

Epidemiology Of Orthopaedic Admissions at Madhesh Institute Of Health Sciences (MIHS), Janakpur, Nepal, Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract: Introduction: Majority of admissions in Orthopaedics ward are due to fractures. But there are many other reasons for which a patient could potentially get admitted in the Orthopaedics ward. The goal of this retrospective study was to analyze the spectrum of Orthopaedics admissions to MIHS which is a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This retrospective study was carried out in the department of orthopaedics at MIHS. The data were collected from the hospital record in the orthopaedic ward to analyse the spectrum of orthopaedic admissions over six months period.

Result: Total number of admissions over six months period was 115. There were 80 males and 35 female patients in the ratio of 2.7. The average age of patients was 41.6 years. Trauma accounted for 93% (107) admissions followed by infections 5% (6) and tumors 2% (2). The ratio of open to closed fracture was 0.09. There were 63% (67) lower limb trauma cases and 37% (40) upper limb trauma cases. Fracture incidence was higher in males than females until 50 years of age after which the trend was almost same. 21- 50 years of age was the most vulnerable group for fractures which accounted for almost more than 50% of total trauma cases. Road traffic accidents and fall from standing height were the most common mechanisms of injury among males and females respectively.

Conclusion: The most common reason for Orthopaedics admission was trauma followed by infections. High velocity injury like RTA was the most common mechanisms of injury among males whereas trivial injury like fall from the standing height was the most common mode of injury among female patients.

Keywords: Epidemiology, Orthopaedics admission, tertiary care Centre, Nepal.

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Introduction

There are various reasons for which a patient could get potentially admitted to the orthopaedic ward in any hospital. Orthopaedic admissions include both patients with trauma and non trauma like infections, deformity, tumors, arthritis, PIVD etc. Increase in the number of osteoporotic fractures among older population has been one of the major reasons for changing pattern of orthopaedic admissions in the hospitals. (1) Trauma injury is the leading cause of mortality and hospitalization worldwide and the leading cause of potential years of productive life lost (2). The burden of road traffic accidents has escalated gradually in Nepal and is a common cause of injury and trauma (3). With a worldwide aging population osteoporotic fragility fractures are increasing over time with associated comorbid conditions like diabetes mellitus, hypertension, COPD and cardiac problems (4). This will also help the team to keep high index of suspicion with regards to the possibility of other associated fractures or system involvement so that these can be identified and treated promptly. Knowledge of the entire trauma workload at tertiary care hospital is key to not only manage resources but to also tailor training opportunities for surgeons and predict areas where allocation of resources could improve patient care within the constraints of the current hospital budget. We evaluated the admissions by the orthopaedic surgery service in terms of demographics, mechanisms of injury, and orthopaedic diagnoses for six months at MIHS.

Research Methodology

We undertook a retrospective epidemiological study of orthopaedics patients admitted to a single centre Madhesh institute of health science between September 2022 to March 2023. The data were collected from the hospital admission book in the orthopaedic ward. We included all patients who were admitted under the direct care of the orthopaedic team, irrespective of what treatment they ultimately ended up having. We excluded the patients who were consulted on for other specialties or those who were only reviewed in the Emergency Department but then subsequently discharged or referred from the hospital. All diagnosis were grouped into four different categories namely trauma, infections, deformity and tumors. Trauma was further divided into upper limb and lower limb trauma. All these categories were reviewed and their epidemiologic trends were noted. Microsoft Excel was used for further analysis.

Results

There were 115 patients admitted under the orthopaedic team during the study period of six months duration. Male to female ratio was 2.7. (figure 1)

The average age of these patients was 41.6 years. There were maximum number of patients in the age group 21-30yrs.

Trauma accounted for 93%(107) admissions followed by infections 5%(6) and tumors 2%(2).(figure 2)

The ratio of open to closed fractures was 0.09(9%).(figure 3)

There were 67(63%) lower limb trauma cases and 40(37%) upper limb trauma cases.(figure 4)

The fracture incidence was higher among males than females until 50 years of age after which the the gender ratio was almost same.(figure 5)

Road traffic accident and fall from standing height were the most common mechanisms of injury among males and females respectively.

Discussion

we found the major cause for orthopaedic admission was trauma followed by infection which is similar to the study done by Mishra et al.(5) Injury occurred more frequently among males than females which is consistent with data from several studies. One of the possible reasons for this include greater number of vehicles driven by males and more participation in high risk activities, i.e. sports and work(6)

The average age of patients in our study was 41.6 years . In our study Trauma and fractures were predominantly highest in 21-30 years of age group whereas 20 – 49 years of age group comprised more than half of trauma and fractures. In the study conducted by Ganveer et al. similar findings were reported(7).

In our study, we also evaluated the Age & Gender specific incidences of Trauma and Fractures. Fracture incidence was higher in males than females until 50 years of age after which the trend was almost same. In the study done by Staa et

al. they also found fracture incidence was greater among men than women until age 50 years of age(8). One of the reasons for this difference in incidence of fractures could be due to high prevalence of osteoporosis with aging population.

There were more lower limb trauma cases compared to upper limb trauma cases in our study which was different from the study done by Mishra et al where they found predominantly upper limb trauma cases(5). Our findings however were similar to the study done by Taylor et al. and Dulal et al(9,10). The incidence of open fracture was 9% which was similar to the study done by Wang et al. where they found the incidence of open fracture to be 8.5%.(11)

Conclusion

Although trauma and fractures were the most common reasons for orthopaedic admission at our center there are also many other injuries/morbidities, which may necessitate admission. Males in the age group 21-30 years were predominantly involved in RTA resulting in fractures and trauma. After 50 years of age fractures showed almost equal incidence between males and females.

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